

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

USING INFORMATIONAL - COMMUNICATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

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Abstract

The problem of forming a scientific-informational medium as a way to raise efficacy of studying stomatological subjects by the students of stomatological faculty is represented in the article. Experience of using information communicative technologies in higher medical establishments has been analyzed.

Keywords: information communicative technology, educational-informational environment.

Introduction. The socio-economic transformations taking place in Ukraine, the world trends of humanization, integration and globalization of society have determined new priorities for the development of the educational sector. The national doctrine of education development states that one of the main aspects of education reform is the introduction of modern pedagogical and scientific-methodical achievements into the educational process, and one of the main ways to improve the content of education is the wide application of information and communication technologies [1].

Today, studying at a higher medical educational institution is a rather complex and multifaceted process. Every year, the amount of information that a student must learn increases, which forces him to look for modern and perfect ways of organizing educational activities. New learning technologies are introduced into the educational process, and information resources are expanded. These innovations, based on the information infrastructure, change the approach, character and teaching method of the academic discipline. In recent years, the equipment of computer equipment in educational institutions of our country has improved significantly [2]. The overhead projector with static slides was replaced by digital projectors, which significantly expanded the arsenal of multimedia technologies and opened up new opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Modern telecommunication systems change the approaches and methods of presenting educational information, make it possible to influence different groups of perception organs, creating an effective educational environment with organization based on the individual capabilities and needs of students [3,4].

The problem of the use of multimedia technologies in the educational process has been widely and fruitfully investigated in the scientific and scientific-methodological literature of recent decades, however, the problem of forming an educational and informational environment adequate to the requirements of the time will remain one of the most relevant in didactics for a long time [5].

The aim of the study. The purpose of our research was didactic substantiation and development of a comprehensive system of using information and communication technologies (ICT) in the process of studying dental disciplines by students of higher educational institutions.

Materials and methods. We have developed an educational and methodological complex, which includes lectures, practical and seminar classes and is aimed at increasing the effectiveness of studying children's therapeutic dentistry by students of the dental faculty through the wide use of ICT.

Discussion of research results. The search for approaches to increase the effectiveness of lectures involved the development of a system of multimedia lectures on children's therapeutic dentistry. In our opinion, the main advantage of the multimedia lecture course is the interactive interaction of the teacher with the student audience. Hardware and software tools provide simultaneous playback of lecture material and provide the opportunity to communicate with the audience. If necessary, you can stop the image and make additional explanations. A multimedia lecture makes it possible to vary the sequence and form of presentation of educational material, it is relatively easy to return to previously presented diagrams, drawings, photos of various clinical cases and radiographs for clarification or establishing connections with new information.

Today, students attach great importance not only to the content, but also to the form of presentation of the material. Therefore, in our opinion, the use of ICT increases students' interest in the lecture itself, and then in the educational process. Students often first remember not the content of the material, but the form of its presentation, and increasing the level of visibility of the lecture material makes it possible to interest the student in the subject and expand the ways of mastering the material.

Observations show that multimedia lectures increase interest in other forms of information technology use, for example, in distance learning using Internet technologies.

The most modern means of conveying information is the use of electronic media. Our university has cre-

ated a powerful distance learning server, where students have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with information about the educational process, in particular: schedules of practical classes and lectures; materials for preparation for practical and seminar classes (texts, drawings, graphs, diagrams, videos, links to other Internet sources); electronic books and magazines. The availability of educational information in electronic form gives students the opportunity to acquire knowledge at a pace and mode of work convenient for them.

The introduction of the credit-module system of the organization of the educational process intensified the search and development of methods of "standardized control of the theoretical and practical training of the student". In practice, this has led to the widespread use of tests. We use the Moodle distance learning system to organize the control of knowledge and skills. Testing is one of the effective means of assessing students' knowledge and skills and has a number of advantages, namely: promptness of obtaining results; a significant expansion of the range of students who can be tested at the same time; the ability to quickly change the number and composition of test tasks used during testing; automation of the selection of test tasks; automation of assessment determination. However, the main advantage of testing is the significant time savings compared to oral interviews.

The leading role in mastering knowledge belongs to independent work. When planning independent work, the student is guided by the curriculum and methodical recommendations from the academic discipline. The program determines what to pay special attention to, what literature to use. Clear planning and proper organization of students' independent work play a special role in mastering the program material.

It is possible to distinguish two types of independent work of students: classroom independent work that takes place under the control of the teacher and independent work that does not involve the direct control of the teacher (outside the classroom: preparation for practical classes, completing module tests, assessments, etc.). An effective means of strengthening both is the use of information resources. At the current stage, the possibilities of organizing students' independent work are expanding thanks to work with educational programs, test systems, and information databases.

Studies show that the use of the Internet system promotes the development of thinking, changes the style of mental activity, increases the motivation of students to work independently, and promotes the implementation of an individual approach to learning.

The multimedia materials developed by us are widely used in practical classes. Theoretical material,

as a rule, is presented in the form of presentations containing radiographs, photographs of clinical manifestations in the oral cavity of certain diseases, video films in which the principles and methods of treatment of dental blockages are demonstrated. In our opinion, this form of presenting the material is unique, visual, dynamic, increases the active thinking of students, is easy to remember and is able to bring the conditions in the classroom as close as possible to the conditions of the future daily activities of the doctor

Conclusions. Thus, the use of multimedia technologies in the educational process is a powerful tool for presenting information in a visual and accessible form and makes it possible to implement a person-oriented approach to education. The principle of visibility is one of the most important in education, and ICT makes it possible to make almost every element of the educational material. Digital projectors provide wide opportunities for illustration - all visual information on the computer monitor can be displayed on the screen - audio, video films and all kinds of animations.

Our conducted research shows that the depth and level of assimilation of educational material increases significantly when using a didactically justified system of information and communication tools.

References

1. Khomenko K. P. Formuvannia profesiinoi kompetentnosti maibutnikh likariv. Humanitarnyi visnyk Pereiaslav-Khmelnyskoho derzh. ped. un-tu im. Hryhoriia Skovorody. 2015;36(62):321-330.
2. Lienkova OO, Morokhovets HYu, Mishchenko SV. Formuvannia informatsiino-komunikatsiinykh kompetentsii maibutnikh likariv na zasakh vykorystannia kompiuternykh tekhnolohii u navchalnomu protsesi. Aktualni problemy suchasnoi medytsyny. 2015;3(51):264-269.
3. Myslovska SK. Pidhotovka studentiv medychnykh VNZ do vykorystannia in-formatsiinykh tekhnolohii u profesiinii diialnosti. Naukovi zapysky Vinnyts-koho derzhavnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu imeni Mykhaila Kotsiubynskoho. 2015; 43:261-265.
4. Saienko MS, Morokhovets HYu. Vykorystannia informatsiino-komunikatsiinykh tekhnolohii u maibutnii profesiinii diialnosti v protsesi vyvchennia medychnoi informatyky. Vyshcha shkola. 2018; 3:18-21.
5. Vakulenko DV, Kravets NO, Dobrovolska AM, Klymuk NYa. Use of modern information and communication technologies in the medical education industry of Ukraine. Medychna osvita. 2019; 3.